

THE COMBINED EFFECT OF MECHANICAL STRESS AND CHEMICAL ENVIRONMENTS ON CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED PEEK LAMINATES CONTAINING A CIRCULAR HOLE

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ABSTRACT

Quasi-isotropic carbon fibre / PEEK laminates containing holes were immersed in dry air, jet fuel, water, and dichloromethane, under tensile, flexural and (in some cases) compressive loads. The effect on the sorption rate was studied as a function of the (constant) strain applied. The specimens were then broken in tension. Strength and modulus retention were noted. The nature and magnitude of the load had little effect on the failure mode, but considerable effect on the strength retention, and damage was sometimes initiated in the vicinity of the holes. Critical strain levels for damage initiation in dichloromethane are reported. Brief observations were also made about unidirectional laminates, without holes.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced polyether ether ketone (PEEK) was developed by ICI under the name APC-2 as a potential aerospace material. Similar materials, with and without fibre reinforcement, have since found other potential applications, some of which require excellent chemical resistance. The anti-corrosion properties of PEEK and similar polyaryl polymers such as PEKK have recently been reviewed in some detail [1]. The most significant variations in solvent resistance arise chiefly from differences in matrix crystallinity [2] arising in turn either from cooling rate variations or from small details of chemical structure. Crystalline forms of PEEK have proved very resistant to many organic solvents, as well as having very low moisture absorption compared with commercially available thermosetting resins.

It is important to consider the effect of a combination of mechanical stress and chemical environment on solvent uptake rates, damage initiation thresholds and retention of mechanical properties. This paper reports some data for quasi-isotropic APC-2 and, to a much lesser extent,

for equivalent unidirectional laminates.

EXPERIMENTAL

The environments chosen were (i) water, because it is ubiquitous (ii) jet fuel, because of its relevance to aviation applications and (iii) dichloromethane. The last-mentioned liquid was chosen partly because of its notorious record of damaging most polymers exposed to paint strippers, and partly because dichloromethane probably represents one of the most damaging of the common organic solvents, by virtue of its molecular size, hydrogen bonding index and solubility parameter. Dry air was used as a control environment. The samples in dry air and dichloromethane were subjected to tensile, 4-point flexural and compressive loads under constant strain conditions, but the samples immersed in water and jet fuel were subjected only to tensile and flexural loads.

LAMINATES

The APC-2 was supplied by ICI as 8 and 16-ply unidirectional sheets, and as 8 and 32-ply quasi-isotropic (i.e. $[-45^{\circ}/0^{\circ}/+45^{\circ}/90^{\circ}]_s$) laminates, with XAS/AS-4 carbon fibres as reinforcement. The carbon fibre volume fraction was determined and found to be 0.61. The laminate thickness was 0.125 mm per ply. The void content was estimated by reflected light microscopy as typically less than 0.1%; very occasionally it was nearer 0.5%. The average crystallinity of the matrix was estimated at 30% by density gradient and X-ray diffraction techniques. All panels were C-scanned before being dried to constant weight over silica gel, under vacuum at 50°C. This pre-conditioning took a minimum of three weeks. The samples were machined with a water-cooled diamond saw, and typical sections were examined under scanning electron microscopy to check for defects.

ENVIRONMENTAL EXPOSURE UNDER LOAD

The temperature of the environments was 23°C. For quasi-isotropic laminates, the period of exposure was 150 days for tensile and 4-point bending strains, but only 28 days for compression because the damage induced was much greater. Unidirectional (axial and transverse) specimens were subjected to 4-point bending only, and for 100 days. Specimen dimensions were as given in Table 1.

The quasi-isotropic specimens (but not the unidirectional ones) each had one centrally placed hole 4 mm in diameter drilled to provide a stress concentrator.

All the loads were applied by mounting the specimens into suitably designed stainless steel jigs [3] and immersing each entire jig in the test liquid. The flexural jigs were of the 4-point bending type, conforming with ASTM-D790, and the support span to thickness ratio was 60:1. The strain levels were those in the outer (tensile) surfaces, calculated from the beam deflection, which was measured using a removable dial gauge.

The tensile and compressive jigs were fitted with load cells to monitor any fall in load at constant strain. These load cells had to be protected from the environments or the signals produced would be erroneous. The bonding area was first cleaned thoroughly, and a cyanoacrylate cement was applied as a thin layer. Connecting leads were soldered to the gauges and securely fixed to the test structure. A tough but flexible and water-resistant putty was then used immediately to protect the strain gauge from moisture in the air. Finally, the putty was surrounded by clingfilm to facilitate handling. Washers and a locking nut were used to prevent the loading mechanism from applying a shear load to the strain gauge assembly. Unstressed

control specimens were also tested in the same way.

Table 1. Specimen dimensions

Load in environment	Plies	Lay-up	Thick-ness mm	Length mm	Width mm	Final break mode
Tensile	8	quasi	1	200	25	tension
Comp.	32	quasi	4	200	25	tension
Flexure **	8	quasi	1	100	25	tension
Flexure **	8	0°	1	100	12.5	flexure *
Flexure **	16	0°	2	100	12.5	flexure *
Flexure **	8	90°	1	100	12.5	flexure *
Flexure **	16	90°	2	100	12.5	flexure *

** 4-point loading

* 3-point loading

TENSILE TESTING (QUASI-ISOTROPIC SAMPLES)

The quasi-isotropic specimens were all finally broken to determine residual tensile properties and to observe aspects of the failure modes, using a Zwick 1484 universal testing machine at a crosshead speed of 5 mm/minute and at ambient temperature. Modulus measurements were performed with a removable strain-gauge type extensometer.

Figure 1 The decrease in applied tensile stress caused by relaxation during constant strain experiments with quasi-isotropic APC-2. The environment was dry air, but similar results were found with water, jet fuel and dichloromethane.

FLEXURAL TESTING (UNIDIRECTIONAL SAMPLES)

The 0° and 90° specimens were broken in 3-point bending after the stress-environmental immersion procedure was complete. The span:thickness ratio here was 32:1, and the testing was again carried out using a Zwick 1484 universal testing machine at a crosshead speed of 5 mm/minute and ambient temperature. Several specimens were warped by the solvents, and had to be carefully straightened out before they could be tested in flexure.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION: QUASI-ISOTROPIC SAMPLES

LOAD STABILITY

For the larger strain levels, the tensile and compressive stresses on the quasi-isotropic specimens immersed in air, water and jet fuel fell progressively with time while the strain was held constant. Fig. 1 is typical. It shows the fall in tensile stress on the samples, expressed as a percentage of the original ultimate tensile strength of 8-ply quasi-isotropic laminates, in dry air over a period of about 120 days at 23°C. Normally when $\pm 45^\circ$ carbon -PEEK is held under tension, the angle between fibres and stress axis gradually reduces by a few degrees in a scissor-closing motion. Dichloromethane attacked the load cells, and no load values could be monitored for this liquid, but it must be assumed that the fall in load was much more rapid because of greatly increased solvent uptake.

LIQUID SORPTION

The amount of jet fuel, water and dichloromethane absorbed under tension in a given time increased with the tensile strain applied (see Fig. 2 for the jet fuel case). The free volume theory of Fahmy and Hurt [4] predicts a linear relationship, which held true in our case for tension, at least in water and jet fuel, and even for dichloromethane up to very high strains (about 1.0%), after which some damage occurred around the holes and solvent absorption increased more steeply.

Four-point flexural strain did not increase sorption rates for water or jet fuel (see Fig. 2) in the strain range studied. This is probably because tensile strain increases the capacity of the matrix to absorb liquids, but compressive strain has the opposite effect, and bending is a combination of tensile with an opposing compressive stress which has the opposite effect.

There was a characteristic critical bending strain in dichloromethane, of about 0.5--0.6%, above which there was a much increased sorption rate. The achievement of this strain level was followed by visible damage, also detected by C-scanning, at or near the circular holes in the specimens. The damage increased further with increasing strain. Under compression, the sorption rate of dichloromethane at first decreased with increasing strain, because of free volume reduction, but it sharply increased again after 0.36% strain, as the damage at the holes appeared. This is shown for 32-ply quasi-isotropic laminates in Fig. 3.

TENSILE PROPERTY REDUCTION

Tensile strength and modulus retention data for quasi-isotropic laminates were generally similar. The retention of tensile strength of quasi-isotropic specimens after 150 days under a flexural load is illustrated in Fig. 4 for all the four environments. Only dichloromethane had a major

effect, and even this solvent required a critical strain level of approximately 0.5% --0.6% to be reached before the strength fell drastically. The equivalent data for 150 days tensile loading, followed by tensile fracture, showed no significant distinction between solvents, except that dichloromethane, being much more readily absorbed, had a slight weakening effect from plasticization, below its critical strain level of 1.0%.

Compressive loading showed a low critical strain level (0.36%) above which both the tensile strength and tensile modulus decreased sharply on final destructive testing.

Reductions in modulus were insignificant with water and jet fuel for all stress modes. Only quantities of these two liquids were absorbed, and consequently there was no critical strain level at which damage was induced.

TENSILE FAILURE MODES

All the quasi-isotropic samples showed much the same type of tensile failure, regardless of the environment and stress mode used. There was no sign of matrix crazing. The ultimate strength was highly dependent on the strength of the axial plies, and the failure process always culminated in axial fibre failure as a last step.

The first microdamage was observed in the transverse plies, especially around the stress concentrating hole. Macrocracking in the same transverse plies followed, and their delamination then began, resulting in subsequent delamination and cracking of the $\pm 45^\circ$ plies. After this point, several different developments could occur: firstly, the axial plies could fail, possibly at a surface defect, and if the fibres were closely packed, the failure of one defective fibre could lead to failure of others, with very rapid local straining of the matrix, resulting in brittle failure of the whole laminate. Exceptionally, instances were seen of fibre failure occurring before matrix failure. Alternatively, the axial plies could delaminate from their neighbours, and then the fibres would break; or they were sometimes observed to break without delamination along a 45° line, presumably where ductile shear occurred as a result of interactions between plies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION: UNIDIRECTIONAL LAMINATES

LIQUID SORPTION

As already discussed for quasi-isotropic samples, free volume effects are approximately cancelled out in bending specimens, and the magnitude of the strain applied had little effect on solvent uptake, except where dichloromethane caused microdamage. At high strains, an increase was observed in the amount of dichloromethane absorbed with increasing bending strain. The increased sorption was large enough, and irregular enough, to suggest microcracking in the compression zone, i.e. the upper face. No evidence of matrix crazing was seen. Weight gain through solvent uptake over 100 days was obviously greater in 8-ply laminates as a percentage of sample weight than with the 16-ply ones, and modulus reduction through solvent plasticization was therefore greater too.

The axial (0°) laminates always regained their original geometry on unloading, but the transverse specimens retained a slight kinking after being bent in dry air, and some were very warped after prolonged bending in dichloromethane. They required very careful straightening before final flexural tests.

The fibre-resin interface remained intact after the above treatments.

RESIDUAL FLEXURAL PROPERTIES

Modulus and strength decreases were caused by large dichloromethane uptakes. As expected, microdamage (inferred from large and irregular increases in solvent uptake) was caused at lower strains in the transverse specimens than the axial ones. It would be expected to lower the strength. 8-ply transverse laminates showed a slight decrease in mechanical property retention after mechanical loading, even in dry air; the reduction was much more marked in dichloromethane. It was difficult to predict the effect of laminate thickness on flexural property retention; the simple relationship between laminate thickness and solvent uptake was complicated by the fact that thickness changes disturb the stress distribution. Typical results are given in Table 2.

Figure 2 The effect of flexural and tensile strain on the amount of aviation jet fuel absorbed in 150 days at 23°C. by quasi-isotropic APC-2.

CONCLUSIONS

The effect of liquid sorption, together with three different stress modes, on the mechanical properties of quasi-isotropic APC-2 has been studied. Sorption of dichloromethane is much more extensive than that of water or jet fuel, and the solvent-related effects are therefore more marked. The high solvent absorption was associated with a critical strain level above which sorption further accelerated as a result of damage initiation. The strain at which this occurred depended on the stress mode. A tensile stress during liquid immersion increases the sorption rate with all the liquids, whereas flexure has no effect except with dichloromethane. Compressive stresses reduce sorption at low strains, but increase it greatly above the critical strain level. None of the stress modes employed affects the final tensile failure mode much, but after a compressive loading period, tensile tests produced delamination at a relatively low tensile strain.

Unidirectional laminates also demonstrated a critical flexural strain above which dichloromethane induced microdamage; the strain level was smaller for transverse than for axially oriented laminates.

Typical examples of reductions in flexural strength and modulus of unidirectional laminates after immersion in dichloromethane under load have been reported.

Figure 3 The amount of dichloromethane absorbed in 28 days at 23°C by quasi-isotropic APC-2 decreases at first with increasing strain applied, but then increases after a critical strain of 0.36% is reached.

Figure 4 The reduction in tensile strength of quasi-isotropic laminates after 150 days under 4-point bending in four different environments at 23°C. Only dichloromethane had a large effect.

Table 2. Residual 3-point bending strength and modulus of unidirectional laminates: typical results after 100 days at 23°C under 4-point bending

Orient'n.	Plies	Environment	Strain %	% retention flex strength	% retention flex modulus	% w/w absorbed
0	16	air	0	100	100	0
0	8	air	0.4	95	99	0
0	16	air	0.8	92	101	0
0	8	CH ₂ Cl ₂	0	89p	96	1.1
0	16	CH ₂ Cl ₂	0	91	108	0.6
0	16	CH ₂ Cl ₂	0.4	90p	95	1.1
0	8	CH ₂ Cl ₂	0.8	63s	81p	0.9
90	8	air	0.4	87p	96	0
90	16	air	0.8	87p	80p	0
90	8	CH ₂ Cl ₂	0.4	55s	71s	2.6
90	16	CH ₂ Cl ₂	0.8	65s	60s	1.6

Figures followed by s represent the (statistically) most significant differences from the controls, as indicated by the Mann-Whitney test. Figures followed by p represent possibly significant differences and the remainder could not be classified as significant.

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REFERENCES

1. G. Pritchard, "Anti-corrosion polymers: PEEK, PEKK and other polyaryls", RAPRA Review Report, RAPRA Technology Ltd., Shawbury, Shropshire, UK (1995)
2. A. Arzak, J. I. Eguiazabal and J. Nazabal, *J. Mater. Sci.*, **28**, 12, 3272-6, (1993)
3. S. J. Randles, "The solvent resistance of aromatic polymer composites", PhD thesis, Kingston Polytechnic, Surrey, UK (November 1990).
4. A.A. Fahmy and J. C. Hurt, *Polymer Composites*, **1**, 2, 77-80 (1980).